

Adaptive Gait Generation for Lower Limb Exoskeletons

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Abstract—Assistive Lower Limb Exoskeletons (LLEs) represent a promising technology for individuals who have lost lower limb control. However, current LLEs have limitations, mainly relying on predefined limb movements without considering the surrounding environment. This work aims to develop a solution addressing this limitation through three modules. The Robotic Vision module detects the environment, locates the exoskeleton, and selects foothold positions. The Collision-Free Foot Trajectory Generator (CFFTG) generates obstacle-aware trajectories. The Kinematic Model module calculates a compliant Center of Mass (CoM) trajectory and performs inverse kinematics for motor control, enabling collision-free walking.

Index Terms—Lower Limb Exoskeleton, Artificial Intelligence, Gait generation, Gait Planning, Computer Vision.

Fig. 1. Overview of the gait generation scheme.

I. INTRODUCTION

Assistive lower-limb exoskeletons (LLEs) are wearable robots designed to help individuals with lower limb impairments regain the ability to walk [1]. While some exoskeletons are already available on the market [2], [3], their use is mainly limited to clinical or research settings [4]. This limitation arises because most commercial LLEs rely on pre-programmed walking patterns (or, at most, individualized for each user) [5], which are not suitable for diverse everyday environments. Existing solutions offer predefined modes for different terrains [1] but often require manual switching [6] and lack real-time adaptation to environmental obstacles. To address these issues, a novel vision-based control approach for obstacle avoidance in LLEs is proposed. It uses an RGB-D camera to detect obstacles, localize the robot, and compute foothold positions based on safety constraints. Additionally, an iterative Collision-Free Foot Trajectory Generator (CFFTG) and a Center of Mass (CoM) kinematic model calculate joint angles to produce a collision-free gait pattern.

II. ROBOTIC VISION MODULE

The Robotic Vision module is in charge of extracting notable information from the visual perception provided by the stereo camera (in form of a point cloud). First, the ground plane is detected through the use of the RANSAC algorithm [7]; in this way, ground plane and obstacle points are separated. Afterwards, the module will align the point cloud with the robot frame (whose origin is located between the feet of the LLE with the Y-axis parallel to the walking direction) by evaluating the distance and orientation between the camera

and the ground: in this way, the position and orientation of the LLE's Center of Mass (CoM) can be inferred. This information, along with the values of the motor encoders, is sufficient to determine the pose of the LLE with respect to the perceived environment. Subsequently, the next step position is computed: to do so, the candidate ground points are given a score based on the distance from the LLE (e.g. points related to steps which are too short or too large are scored lower) and the nearby obstacle points (e.g. the taller the obstacle, the larger the distance required to reach the maximum score). Then, a sliding window approach is employed to identify the foothold positions that maximizes the score of the points within it. Finally, the module will output the pose of the robot, the pose of the obstacles in line with the swing foot and the chosen foothold position for the swing foot.

III. COLLISION-FREE FOOT TRAJECTORY GENERATOR

After having acquired the visual information, the CFFTG module is in charge of computing the optimal trajectory that brings the swing foot to the position provided by the Robotic Vision module. To do so, the algorithm's goal is to find the peak of the trajectory that yields a collision-free path. In order to do that, two gaussian distributions σ_h , σ_v are employed to output the horizontal and vertical position of the peak. When a trajectory improves upon the previous ones (i.e. by having less intersection with obstacles or, if there is no intersection, by keeping a larger distance between the foot and obstacles) the mean and variance of the random variables are updated so that the search space is narrowed around the best peak position.

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Algorithm 1 CFFTG pseudo-code

```
1: Initialize Gaussian Random Variables  $\sigma_h, \sigma_v$ 
2: Initialize safe distance
3: Initialize scaling factor (must be  $> 1$ )
4: Initialize trajectory, best trajectory
5: stop  $\leftarrow$  false
6: while stop = false do
7:   Compute trajectory with peak obtained by drawing from
     distributions  $\sigma_h, \sigma_v$ 
8:   Evaluate the intersection between trajectory and obstacles
9:   Evaluate minimum distance between trajectory and obstacles
10:  if trajectory doesn't intersect obstacles then
11:    if minimum distance  $>$  Safe Distance then
12:      stop  $\leftarrow$  true
13:    else if minimum distance  $>$  best trajectory minimum
     distance then
14:      Mean of  $\sigma_h$  = current value drawn from  $\sigma_h$ 
15:      Mean of  $\sigma_v$  = current value drawn from  $\sigma_v$ 
16:      Variance of  $\sigma_h$  = Variance of  $\sigma_h$  / scaling factor
17:      Variance of  $\sigma_v$  = Variance of  $\sigma_v$  / scaling factor
18:    end if
19:  else
20:    if intersection is less than best trajectory then
21:      Mean of  $\sigma_h$  = current value drawn from  $\sigma_h$ 
22:      Mean of  $\sigma_v$  = current value drawn from  $\sigma_v$ 
23:      Variance of  $\sigma_h$  = Variance of  $\sigma_h$  / scaling factor
24:      Variance of  $\sigma_v$  = Variance of  $\sigma_v$  / scaling factor
25:    end if
26:  end if
27: end while
28: return best trajectory
```

IV. KINEMATIC MODEL

The kinematic model is in charge of producing a suitable CoM trajectory and perform inverse kinematic calculations to obtain the respective angular trajectories that will be sent to the lower level control. The hip trajectory has been designed based on the crank-connecting rod mechanism [8], since it well represents the slight extension that is performed by the support knee during the swing, opposing to the Inverted Pendulum models that are usually employed for the same task, which assume a fixed bend of the support knee during the swing. After having produced the hip trajectory, the knees trajectories can be inferred through trigonometry calculations given hip and foot trajectories, and inverse kinematics calculations are then performed to obtain the angles sent to the motor controller.

V. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

Preliminary experiments both in real scenarios (Robotic Vision module) and simulation (CFFTG and kinematic model) are showing promising results. Acquisition performed with the Intel Realsense D435 camera have returned the expected results, with a mean positional error of 2 cm calculated on both robot and obstacles pose estimation. As it can be seen in figure 2, the CFFTG shows the ability to correctly output

Fig. 2. CFFTG simulation in different scenarios.

collision-free trajectories in various scenarios. In future work, the whole adaptive gait generation will be tested on different exoskeletons to demonstrate the generality of the proposed approach.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this dissemination, a novel solution for Adaptive Gait Planning through the use of visual perception has been proposed; the solution is able to autonomously produce a suitable walking gait even in the presence of obstacles. At the moment, experiments on a real LLE are being performed to assess the validity of the solution in a real scenario.

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